

Identification of prominent secondary metabolites by TLC in *Sida acuta* Burm. from unexplored Gadchiroli District of Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

Phyto-medicine is the plant-derived medicine on which most of the developing countries are depends. To preserve an ancient culture and traditional knowledge of phytomedicine, need to identify the secondary metabolites of plants in forest cover land. In Gadchiroli district of Maharashtra *Sida acuta* is a widely used medicinal plant and known for its anti-inflammatory and anticancerous activity in local tribes. To understand the phytochemicals in the *S. acuta* and to collect the scientific evidence for the therapeutic used present investigation has undertaken. Methanolic extract of *S. acuta* Burm. whole plant has been studied to identified secondary metabolites by thin-layer chromatography using hot solvent extraction method. The present investigation reveals prominent availability of Terpenoids, Phenols, Hydroxycinnamic acid, Tannins, Coumarin and Lignan. More investigation needed to study the activity of the secondary metabolites in *S. acuta* for possible use in various diseases.

Keywords: *S. acuta*; secondary metabolites; TLC

From the 20th century, human struggling for the remediation of the dreadful and major challenging diseases like AIDS, cancers even in the 21st century. Struggling with the investigation on derived and synthetic medicines, researchers now searching for natural remedies from plant sources (Korekar, Kumar, and Ugale 2019) .

The number of plants has been reported for the treatment of various diseases in Ayurveda and unani shows anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and anti-cancerous activity (Akhtar and Swamy 2018). *Sida acuta* (Malvaceae) has been used commonly as a traditional remedy. Apart from the treatment of diarrhoea, malarial, gastrointestinal dysentery, fevers, asthma and inflammation

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(Akbar 2020; Mah, Teh, and Ee 2017), used commonly as a traditional remedy. Apart from the treatment of diarrhoea, malarial, gastrointestinal dysentery, fevers, asthma and inflammation (Akbar 2020; Mah, Teh, and Ee 2017), *Sida acuta* has shown prominent anti-cancerous activity (Fadeyi et al. 2013). A brief review by Dinda et al 2015 reveals the presence of about 142 chemical constituents from different *Sida* species (Dinda et al. 2015), recently 121 active chemical constituents were listed out in *Sida* species, of which 89 were discovered in the last five years (Rodrigues and Oliveira Morais 2020) of which alkaloids, flavonoids and ecdysteroids are the predominant groups. To collect the scientific evidence for the presence of the secondary metabolites, having therapeutic used the present investigation has undertaken.

Gadchiroli district in Maharashtra state located at 20.10°N 80.0°E selected as the study area, as the district has the highest proportion of forest

Figure 1: Study area and distribution of *Sida acuta* in Gadchiroli district of Maharashtra (Source: <http://www.mahapolice.gov.in/mahapolice/jsp/temp/Gadchirolimap.jsp>)

area and mineral deposits in the state (Census 2011) (Figure 1) with more than 50% population in the rural area which depending on the traditional practices for health care.

Sida acuta Burm. (Malvaceae) is evergreen herbs-under shrubs and known as Chikna in Marathi. *Sida* species are widely distributed throughout India and most tropical countries. *Sida acuta* species found abundant in suburban

areas and rural area on plain wasteland and roadside. The species having softwood, with 40-60cm in height comprising the bright yellow coloured flower (Figure 2).

Whole plant materials were collected freshly from the study area and then washed thoroughly with tap water followed by a sterile distilled water rinse. The whole plant was shade dried at room temperature and crushed to a fine powder by a mechanical process.

Table 1: Plant characteristics and botanical description of <i>Sida acuta</i>	
Botanical description	Plant characters
Habitat	Plain waste land, roadside
Plant type	Under shrubs
Foliage	Evergreen
Root	Tap root
Stem	Soft wooded
Leaf type	Leaves linear, lanceolate
Height	40-60 cm tall
Flower color	Yellow

Table 2: Detection of secondary metabolites from methanolic extract of <i>S. acuta</i>									
Secondary metabolites	↓	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Total band
Band number	→								
Terpenoids	Color	PY	GGr	GGr	Y	Y	Gr		06
	Rf	0.060	0.155	0.310	0.391	0.641	0.675		
Phenol's	Color	BG	BG						02
	Rf	0.75	0.98						
Hydroxycinnamic acid	Color	DG	LY	DG	DG	DG			05
	Rf	0.250	0.553	0.669	0.714	0.982			
Tannin's	Color	BG							01
	Rf	0.89							
Coumarin	Color	B	Y						02
	Rf	0.836	0.983						
Lignan	Color	P	P	P	P				04
	Rf	0.190	0.203	0.756	0.993				

GGr-Green Grey, V-Violet, P-Purple, Br-Brown, LV-Light violet, LY- Light Yellow, LG- Light Green, LGr-Light grey, GG-Green grey
Y-Yellow, Gr-Grey, B-Blue, PGr-Purple grey

Figure 2: Detection of Secondary metabolites in Methanolic extract of *Sida acuta* plants after derivatisation

The powder stored in the airtight container until analysis. The dried powder forwarded for hot solvent (methanol) extraction by Soxhlet (Harborne 1984). Whole plant methanolic extract dried at 45°C. The colour of the extract was recorded and proceed for phytochemical and pharmacological screening. TLC and solvent system made (Harborne 1984). The TLC plates prepared by applying silica gel G slurry (1:2 w/v) in distilled water by the aluminum applicator on 10 x 20 cm thin glass plate. The plates were activated by heating at 50°C overnight. The spots were applied on plates equidistantly with the help of micropipette, 2 cm above the lower edge of the plate. The distance between spots was 1.5 cm, the line drawn at the distance of 10 cm from the spots. The spots were dried and plates placed in a saturated sealed chamber containing solvent system and derivative by applying derivatizing agent (Wagner and Bladt 1996) .

Thin-layer chromatography reveals the presence of secondary metabolites. After application of derivatizing agent, the colour appeared on the TLC plates confirm the presence of Terpenoids, Phenols, Hydroxycinnamic acid, Tannins, Coumarin and Lignan (Fig. 3 and Table 1). Present investigation confirms the presence of prominent secondary metabolites (Rodrigues and Oliveira Morais 2020). Solvent extract possessed relatively high pharmacological activities like anti-inflammatory activity (Mah, Teh, and Ee 2017; Sutradhar et al. 2008; Dinda et al. 2015; Konaté et al. 2012) , antimicrobial activity (Ekpo and Etim 2009; Konaté et al. 2012; Karou et al. 2003) . Extracts also possessed acute toxicity (Govindarajan 2010; Karou et al. 2003; Adesina et al. 2020) and cytotoxicity (Mah, Teh, and Ee 2017; Adesina et al. 2020; Rodrigues and Oliveira Morais 2020; Kanthal, Bhar, and Ravali 2017) and also antiplasmodial activity (Adesina et al. 2020) . Flavones have been tested for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity in previous study (Sutradhar et al. 2008)

Gadchiroli district is a remote area and most of its are unexplored due to Naxalite activities (Rajput 2019). In the present investigation, we analyzed secondary metabolites by TLC. Though the finding is nor varies much from the previous study, the area, type and genotype can affect phytochemicals variations in the plants (Mostafavi, Asadi-Gharneh, and Miransari 2018). As most of the members of Malvaceae family,

Sida acuta is cross-pollinated plants (Raju and Rani 2016), therefore there are possibilities of the change in genotypes and hence in phytochemicals. Therefore, the possibility of change in the composition of phytochemicals is never been neglected.

Present investigation confirms the presence of Terpenoids, Phenols, Hydroxycinnamic acid, Tannins, Coumarin and Lignan. Therefore, *Sida acuta* will be a promising drug for the treatment of various diseases like cancer and need more investigation on the in vitro activity of phytochemicals. We suggest further work on the detailed study on the activities of phytochemicals which will contributed to research. Further, the plates were introduced in saturated sealed chamber containing solvent system. Derivatizing Reagent Preparation carried out as per method previously reported (Wagner And Bladt, 1996).

Thin layer chromatography is important and efficient method used to separate and identify secondary metabolites on the basis of RF value from medicinal plants. Chromatographic separations take advantage of the fact that different substances are partitioned differently between two phases, a mobile phase and a stationary phase. Thin-layer chromatography is a chromatography technique used to separate non-volatile mixtures. In thin layer chromatography, or TLC, the mobile phase is a liquid and the stationary phase is a solid absorbent.

Plant metabolites are grouped into two classes Primary and secondary metabolites. In Present investigation for the separation of constituents and its group identification first method used was TLC. Primary metabolites are synthesized by the cell because they are indispensable for their growth.

Secondary metabolites are compounds produced by an organism that are not required for primary metabolic processes, although they can have important ecologic and other functions. They include drugs, fragrances, flavor, dye, pigments, pesticides and food additives with applications in agriculture, industry and pharmaceuticals. In Plant Kingdom secondary metabolites divides into three groups: 1. Terpenoids such as monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, triterpenes, steroids, essential oils and carotenoids. 2. Phenolics such as phenol's and

phenolic acids, phenylpropanoids, flavonoids, anthocyanins, tannin's, quinone pigments, etc. 3. Nitrogen compounds such as alkaloids.

A detailed study for six secondary metabolites groups were undertaken which provides good results in the form of Rf values and colour of band before derivatisation which are presented in following subsection. *S. acuta* has been involved in number of traditional practices and found to be useful in treatment of ulcers, gastric disorders, fever, malaria, skin disease, dysentery, and many more. This plant also highlighted prominent features such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer and other. To elaborate further worker, Tcheghebe O. T. et al., (2017) recorded the prominent presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannin's, coumarins, phenolic compounds, sesquiterpenes, glycosides and flavonoids remained present in *S. acuta* which certainly put this plant in ethnomedicinal category.

Figure 2: *Sida acuta* flower

In the conclusion thin layer chromatography analysis and related evidences gathered from the tribal records indicated that prescribed plants by the herbal healers certainly contains number of bio active compounds which are systematically reported by number workers and justify the present work also which will certainly be useful in human therapies.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

No Additional information is available for this paper.

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